

Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)

Towards the development of agroecology in Europe

Deliverable report D5.6 – EU Agroecology strategy

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This deliverable proposes the main set of recommendations associated with the specific promotion of Agroecology in the CAP considering both the agroecosystem and the social perspective. It defines **agroecology agroecosystem based definition** as the agricultural spatial and temporal biodiversity preservation, enhancement, use and integration at multiple scales to increase resources use efficiency while improving ecosystem services delivery. The biodiversity temporal use is associated with the crop and livestock rotation, while the biodiversity spatial use and protection is linked to the crop and livestock diversification and soil protection. **The agroecology social based definition** is detailed as the dynamic social construction within and among actors that fosters knowledge and activities exchange processes and continuous learning among different stakeholders: producers, processors, retailers, advisors, researcher and consumers aiming at implementing the agroecology main principles or elements. The social movement associated with the agroecological elements should be fostered based on the horizontal knowledge sharing among peers and stakeholders, collaboration and cooperation among peers and stakeholders and the promotion of short and diversified value chains. The deliverable also analyses the relationship of agroecology with the environment and social conditionality, the ecoschemes and the rural development programmes attending to the beforementioned definitions. **A set of 12 recommendations are provided to foster agroecology by the CAP** and were the following: Recommendation 1: Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition

Agroecology agroecosystem based is defined as the Agroecology agroecosystem level definition is the agricultural spatial and temporal biodiversity preservation, enhancement, use and integration at multiple scales to increase resources use efficiency while improving ecosystem services delivery ».

Recommendation 2: Crop rotation

The promotion of crop rotation should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple temporary scales including the short, intermediate and long term (agroforestry) rotations

Recommendation 3: Livestock rotation

The promotion of crop rotation should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple temporary and spatial scales including the short, intermediate (trastermitance) and long term (trashumance) rotations as a form to optimize the use of the resources and increase land connectivity and therefore enhancing biodiversity

Recommendation 4: Crop diversification

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The promotion of crop diversification should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple scales including intraspecific, the inter-specific with herbaceous-herbaceous and herbaceous-woody perennials combinations (agroforestry).

Recommendation 5: Livestock diversification

The promotion of livestock diversification should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple scales including intraspecific, the inter-specific with to protect the existing livestock biodiversity while promoting farming resilience.

Recommendation 6: Soil sustainable management

The sustainable soil production is essentially obtained through the adequate inputs of organic matter to overcome the intensive farming system soil decapitalization at medium and long term. Crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation and livestock diversification play an important role in obtaining these organic matter inputs without external amendments. The use of forest residues as a way to increase soil organic matter is also an excellent landscape nutrient cycling connection that improves sustainable soil fertility promotion that was traditionally used in Europe. Due to the huge soil degradation and the excess of mineral nutrient applied in European soils, the lack of chemicals use and the nutrient accountability is seen as essential.

Recommendation 7. Food system management

Agroecology social definition is the dynamic social construction within and among actors that fosters knowledge and activities exchange processes and continuous learning among different stakeholders: producers, processors, retailers, advisors, researcher and consumers aiming at implementing the agroecology main principles or elements. The social movement associated with the agroecological elements should be fostered based on the horizontal knowledge sharing among peers and stakeholders, collaboration and cooperation among peers and stakeholders and the promotion of short and diversified value chains.

Recommendation 8: Standards for good agricultural and environmental condition of land (GAEC)

The current state of degradation of European ecosystems makes highly relevant all the GAEC proposals. However, the ones associated with permanent grasslands should be more ambitious and promote the expansion of the extent of this land whenever abandon land on marginal areas exist through extensive livestock farming systems in some Mediterranean areas. Adequate prescribed burning practices ensures shrublands health if carried out in small areas and combined with grazing. No-tillage, minimum tillage and avoiding bare soils are seen as

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a great measure to preserve the carbon but the introduction of woody perennials to enhance soil carbon stocks is needed in some degraded soils. More proactive GAEC initiatives such as buffer strips along water courses, crop rotation and the inclusion of non-productive areas or features in agricultural areas are more suitable for the current EU degraded soils and ecosystems.

Recommendation 9: Statutory management requirement (SMR)

The current state of degradation of European ecosystems, the needs of protecting health and ethically promote animal welfare makes highly relevant all the SMR proposals.

The links of the use of biodiversity to reduce the needs of fertilizers (water protection), and preserve habitats (for birds, flora and fauna) is not clearly shown. Therefore a lack of agroecological, biodiversity nature-based solutions are not linked to the SMR as the first step to reduce the SMR1 to 4 aims.

There is a lack of connection of the biodiversity potential and their respective ecological functions with the food safety and plant protection. SMR 1 to 8 should be clearly linked to crop rotation, crop diversification, soil preservation and adequate livestock grazing to reduce the degradation state of the European ecosystems from the very beginning in the CAP besides what is shown and enlarged in the eco-schemes or rural development methods.

The SMR 9 to 11 should promote grazing as a way to use and promote biodiversity at various levels and recognize the role extensive grazing systems with a per se brand of fulfilment of the animal welfare requisites that are linked to the plot, farm and landscape agroecological practices promotion.

Recommendation 10: Ecoschemes

The ecoschemes list proposed by the European Commission are mostly linked to the agroecological practices associated with crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation, livestock diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration. From those livestock diversification is not presented as part of the ecoschemes. Moreover, there are several practices that may involve all agroecological biodiversity-based practices, but they are not detailed enough. The involvement of forest lands as suppliers of fertility to agronomic land, the use of livestock as a way to increase the nutrient cycling and above all of them to improve soil health should be better detailed.

Recommendation 11: Agroecosystem based Rural Development interventions

The current open rural development interventions associated with the CAP 2023-2027 are mostly linked to the agroecological practices associated with crop rotation, crop

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diversification, livestock diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration. From those livestock rotation is not presented as part of the rural development interventions. There is a lack of promotion of the connectivity among different types of lands by using livestock or forest residues that are incipiently promoted in France and that are needed to fulfil the agroecological principles.

Recommendation 12: Food system based Rural Development interventions

The current open social rural development interventions associated with the CAP 2023-2027 are somehow promoting social agroecological aspects linked to the knowledge transfer and fostering interactions among different types of stakeholders and promoting short value chains. However, this is limited a short number of countries.

1. Introduction

Defining an agroecology strategy should take into account the main international, European and Pan-European strategies taken as commitments by the European Commission while considering the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) as the main driver of the agriculture in Europe funding both agroecology farming and enabling environment activities and therefore Rural Development. Deliverable 5.1 shows how the CAP is aligned the 10 agroecological principles identified by the FAO as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Post-2020 CAP aims (black), FAO agroecology elements (green) and EU linked strategies (red)

Transition to Agroecology has been recently considered by the EU as a form to increase sustainability of the European farming systems. The SCAR-Agroecology group was created

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to work on the definition, relevance, and development of a European partnership in agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. The Agroecology partnership has been launched this year to promote agroecology living labs across the EU.

The agroecological concept is being defined by different institutions considering the important and relevant social movement involved in the agroecology concept associated with a set of practices performed at EU level. The “Agroecology partnership” definition for agroecology a “*dynamic and holistic approach to agriculture considered at the same time a science, a set of practices and a socio-political movement aimed at supporting the transition of agri-food systems towards more sustainable practices. It aims at connecting science, practice and society and to trigger the adoption of a set of policies aimed at sustainable agricultural practices*”. This definition includes several approaches as the practices and the socio-political movement that must be included to indeed reach the needed agroecological transition of food systems in Europe, highlighting the principles of the Farm to Fork strategy. However, this broad definition does not provide concrete practices to be promoted by the CAP linked to land use (arable crops, permanent grasslands, permanent crops and somehow forestry), which is the main basis for CAP payments.

The structure of the CAP aims at transforming EU farming systems into sustainable farming systems at field (plot) level considering the direct payments associated with the Pillar I (conditionality and ecoschemes) and the rural development interventions related to the agroecosystems and social promotion in rural areas. Therefore, as it is now the promotion of agroecology, the recommendations to foster agroecology in Europe should be directly linked to (i) the promotion of sustainable agroecological practices at field level and (ii.) the enhancement of the social part linked to the whole agri-food system.

Considering the transition levels provided by SCAR-Agroecology working group (Figure 2), the current CAP promotion of agroecology in Europe is mainly focussed in the levels 1 and 2 of the “**incremental**” phase associated with the “**agro-ecosystem level**” while the “**transformational**” phase linked to the “**food system level**” is not so relevant for the current CAP. In spite of the weak movement of the EU within the food system level, some Green Deal goals are approaching the level 3 when considering the whole agri-food system.

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Figure 2 Agroecology transition levels (SCAR-AGROECOLOGY, 2022, based on HLPE 2019 and Gliessman 2007).

The current CAP mainly promotes specific farming practices implemented at plot level, while weakly considering, in general the level 3 of the food system involving the redesign of agroecosystems based on ecological processes (i.e. crop rotation, crop diversification). The CAP enables the adequate business environment for agroecological practices at less extent. The development of the list of the set of farm and food system practices is essential to integrate the agroecology principles in the CAP fostering the implementation of the agroecology transition. These practices can be integrated in the temporary and spatial biodiversity use of land and the food system.

The agroecology strategy should also consider the direct payments linked to the land use defined by the CAP (arable crops, permanent grasslands and permanent crops) but also the conditionality and ecoschemes within the Pillar I. Moreover, the agroecology strategy should take into account the existing pathways that promotes agroecological practices while enabling the agroecology environment.

The agroecology strategy is based on a definition of agroecology to be adopted and monitored by policy makers in the different EU member states. Therefore, the deliverable 5.6 will be based on a set of recommendations linked to the incremental and the transformational phase to foster sustainability in Europe across the agroecosystem and food system level in Europe.

2. Agroecology strategy

2.1. Incremental agroecology phase: The agroecosystem level

The agroecosystem level has been approached by the commission since 2007, when the payments per livestock or per agricultural production was transformed towards land use-based payments. For this purpose, the concept of agroecology should be approached from an agroecosystem level perspective based on the “biodiversity” concept.

2.1.1. Defining agroecology from an agroecosystem perspective

The agroecology definition to be considered by the CAP should be based in the biodiversity concept that plays a key role to increase the efficiency of input uses, reducing the use of external inputs, substitute conventional inputs and redesign agroecosystems based on ecological processes. The most powerful tool to reach the agroecology transition should be based on the Biodiversity use linked to the nature-based solutions goals. The agroecology agroecosystem-based definition can be “*the agricultural spatial and temporal biodiversity preservation, enhancement, use and integration at multiple scales to increase resources use efficiency while improving ecosystem services delivery*“. Simply speaking, agroecology identifies **crop rotation** as the temporary use of the biodiversity and the **crop diversification** as the spatial use of the biodiversity, while **soil preservation techniques** such as no tillage, minimum tillage, use of natural inputs are seen as a form of biodiversity **preservation**.

Recommendation 1: Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition

Agroecology agroecosystem based is defined as the Agroecology agroecosystem level definition is the agricultural spatial and temporal biodiversity preservation, enhancement, use and integration at multiple scales to increase resources use efficiency while improving ecosystem services delivery ».

2.1.2. Identifying agroecology biodiversity based-use and preservation practices from an agroecosystem perspective.

The promotion, enhancement, integration and preservation of the biodiversity should be carried out by establishing practices that take into account the habitats for vegetal, livestock and soil components. All them vegetal, livestock and soil agroecological practices should be combined following a holistic approach within the farming systems sustainability concept.

2.1.2.1.- *Crop and livestock rotation and diversification*

Figure 3 shows the main biodiversity based practices linked to the enhancement of **vegetal component**, that can be identified as crop rotation always in the same plot and crop

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diversification either in the same or nearby plot. The vegetal component can be fostered at spatial (crop rotation carried out in the same plot) and the crop diversification developed at the same or nearby plots.

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition

Figure 3 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition practices

2.1.2.1.1. Crop rotation

The **crop rotation** could be split in short (intra-annual), intermediate (between 2 or 5 years) or long term rotation (over 5 years) patterns (Figure 4). The short crop rotation is produced in most intensive farming systems as they try to avoid subsequently winter (with no (cover crops) or with market (catch crops) aims (cereals like oat, rye, wheat, Italian ryegrass or even mix of them with legumes etc..)) and summer crops (maize or sorghum that may be mixed with legumes also (i.e. beans). The intermediate rotation is usually linked to different types of crops such as legumes, cereals, dicotyledons and even fallow land, aiming at reducing pest and diseases and increase the soil health from a biological, chemical and physical perspective due to the inclusion of deep root plants. The long-term rotation with shrub legumes (i.e. *Ulex europeaus*) was traditionally used to improve soil health where they were sown and in the surrounding areas after harvesting and being used as animal bedding to be transformed into a fertilizer. Moreover, the long term crop rotation reduces cereal weeds when the shrub was rotated with cereals. The same is currently done in some Mediterranean areas where herbaceous permanent grasslands -based on annual species- are established to increase fertility for further cereal cropping.

Recommendation 2: Crop rotation

The promotion of crop rotation should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple temporary scales including the short, intermediate and long term (agroforestry) rotations

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition: Crop Rotation

Figure 4 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition crop rotation type practices

2.1.2.1.2 Livestock rotation

The **livestock rotation** is associated with the movement of animals from one plot to another causing land connectivity and enhancing nutrient cycling and the use of the resources. It is essential for the sustainability of farming systems due to the enhancement that grazing causes of the biodiversity (caused by species consumption selection, seeds transport, faeces therefore nutrient deposition in one different areas and release in another plot and trampling). The livestock rotation can be short (within the same farm), intermediate (within the same area also known as trastermitance) and long rotation (in different areas) also known as trashumance. The livestock rotation causes a better matching between vegetal production and animal needs avoiding dependence from external feed resources. This is an excellent form to connect different land uses including croplands, permanent grasslands and forest lands (Figure 5).

Recommendation 3: Livestock rotation

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The promotion of crop rotation should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple temporary and spatial scales including the short, intermediate (trastermitance) and long term (trashumance) rotations as a form to optimize the use of the resources and increase land connectivity and therefore enhancing biodiversity

Table 1 shows the beforementioned main types of rotational crop and livestock based agroecological practices associated with the alternative use of the land in the case of the croplands or the movement of animals across land uses and plots. Agroecological farming systems should combine both animals and crop rotation systems that will enhance the optimization of the nutrient cycling and the biodiversity.

Table 1 Agroecological rotation based systems explanation for croplands and livestock

CROP ROTATION							
Temporary scale							
Practice	Scale	Land use	Temporary scale	Explanation	Main purpose	Description	Example
CROP ROTATION	Same plot (plot scale)	Agriculture	Short rotation	annual	Increase annual production, reduce nitrate leaching	annual crops based: Winter cereal or cover crop+ summer cereal	"wheat or rye or barley or oat or ryegrass" + "maize or sorgum"
		Agriculture	Intermediate rotation	between 2 and 5 years	Reduce pest, weeds, increasing soil health	annual crop based: Cereal + legume + dicot + fallow land	rye or wheat + clover or lucerne + brassica
		Agriculture and/or forestry	Long term rotation	over 5 years	Improve soil health in low productive areas, increase soil carbon	permanent crop based: permanent crop + cereal	example: permanent grassland (7 years) + 3 year cereal or Ulex shrublands 10 years + 3 years cereal
LIVESTOCK ROTATION							
Livestock temporary scale							
Practice	Scale	land use	Croop use	explanation	Main purpose	Description	Example
LIVESTOCK ROTATION	Main Farm grazing basis	agriculture, and/or forestry	arable crops, permanent grasslands, forest land	within farm rotation	increase resource efficiency, biodiversity enhancement, reduce animal production costs, improve soil fertility	Animals rotating within the different land uses farm	Croplands residues grazing after harvesting
	No main farm grazing basis	agriculture, and/or forestry	arable crops, permanent grasslands, forest land	close farm area rotation. Trastermitance	improve soil fertility, resource efficiency, biodiversity enhancement, improve animal productivity, improve grassland quality	Animals rotating in nearby areas close to the farm, including cooperative grazing	Nearby mountains grazing
		agriculture/forestry	arable crops, permanent grasslands, forest land	trashumance	better use of the resources, reducing cost production costs, soil improvement, biodiversity enhancement	Long distance grazing	Cross-region grazing

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition: *Livestock Rotation*

Figure 5 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition livestock rotation type practices

2.1.2.1.3 Crop diversification

The **crop diversification** can be carried out in the same or nearby plots (Figure 6). The crop diversification developed in the same plot implies the use of different varieties and species. The different varieties were used in the past for example to ensure chestnut production in areas with unstable weather associated with transitional climatic areas (Atlantic and Mediterranean in Galicia, Spain) ensuring the lack of damage of frost to the flowering period. The different species can be herbaceous (i.e. legumes and cereals, or mixed swards) and are usually integrating a legume to improve the nitrogen in the soil. When the combination of species includes a woody perennial we are talking about agroforestry increasing soil organic matter. Nearby plot crop diversification is also possible when a diversity of species is mixed in nearby plots aiming at diversify production, but also reducing pest effects and increasing pollination.

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition: Crop Diversification

Figure 6 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition crop diversification type practices

Recommendation 4: Crop diversification

The promotion of crop diversification should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple scales including intraspecific, the inter-specific with herbaceous-herbaceous and herbaceous-woody perennials combinations (agroforestry).

2.1.2.1.4 Livestock diversification

The **Livestock diversification** involves the genetic preservation of breeds and animals (Figure 7) that on the one hand will increase resilience in the livestock farming system and on other hand will contribute to the preservation of the domestic breeds and animals. Farm resilience is based on the different feed needs of animals and breeds that can make them complementary for the use of the resources (i.e. goats and cows) and the type of market products that the different breed and animals can produce, fostering therefore multiple-product farming systems. Biodiversity preservation is highly relevant for Europe that has the 50% of the domestic breeds of the world, half of which are in risk of extinction.

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition: Crop and livestock Diversification

Figure 7 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition crop diversification type practices

Recommendation 5: Livestock diversification

The promotion of livestock diversification should be enhanced by the CAP at multiple scales including intraspecific, the inter-specific with to protect the existing livestock biodiversity while promoting farming resilience.

Table 2 shows the main types of diversification agroecological practices attending to the type of land use spatial scale, description and examples in a summarized form.

Table 2 Agroecological diversification based systems explanation for croplands and livestock

CROP DIVERSIFICATION								
Spatial scale								
Practice	Scale	Land use	Mixture	Mixture type	Main purpose	Description	Example	
CROP DIVERSIFICATION	Same plot (plot scale)	Agriculture	Variety	Mix of crop varieties in the same plot	Increase biotic and abiotic factor resistance	Permanent or annual crops variety mixtures	The use of varieties of chestnut to avoid frost effects in the production of chestnut fruits	
		Agriculture	Species (herbaceous)	Mix of crop species in the same plot	Increase productivity and quality	Mix of legumes and cereals	i.e. mixed sward, vetch + oat	
		Agriculture and/or forestry	Species (herbaceous and woody, therefore silvoarable)	Mix of woody perennials and herbaceous crop species in the same plot	Increase soil fertility, ensure water and temperature conditions for the herbaceous crop, increase soil carbon	Agroforestry	i.e. silvoarable silvopasture	
	nearby plot (farm or landscape scale)	Agriculture and/or forestry	species in patches (silvoarable or silvopasture)	patches distribution	Diversify production ensuring income, reduce pests effects, increase farm climate neutrality (if woody perennials are part of the system), increase soil carbon	crop diversification + agroforestry (if woody perennials are involved)	i.e. patchy landscapes	
LIVESTOCK DIVERSIFICATION								
Spatial scale								
Practice	Scale	land use	crop use	Explanation	Main purpose	Description	Example	
LIVESTOCK DIVERSIFICATION	Mix of livestock breeds	agriculture/forestry	high diversified permanent grasslands including woody perennials	mix of breeds adapted to different types of nutrient requirements (i.e. meat and dairy cows)	improve soil, resource efficiency, biodiversity enhancement, reduce fire risk, protect the environment	Mixed grazing with livestock animals preferring herbaceous or woody perennials	i.e. grazing with meat and dairy cows	
	Mix of livestock species	agriculture/forestry	high diversified permanent grasslands including woody perennials	mix of species adapted to different types of vegetation (woody and herbaceous)	improve soil, resource efficiency, biodiversity enhancement, reduce fire risk, protect the environment	Mixed grazing with livestock animals preferring herbaceous or woody perennials	i.e. grazing with goats and sheep or cows	

2.1.2.2.- Soil physical and chemical promotion

Figure 8 shows the main biodiversity-based practices linked to the enhancement of **soil production**, that can be split in soil physical promotion and soil chemical promotion. The soil physical promotion is associated with the minimum or no tillage when annual species are cropped or the use of deep rooted species included permanent crops. These practices always increase the soil organic matter. With regard to the soil chemical promotion, it can be associated either with the organic fertilizer optimal use (i.e. manure) or the organic amendments (i.e. compost) use with products with a low and high C/N relationship, respectively. Soil health is also maintained by the reduction or avoidance of all types of biocides

Agroecology agroecosystem-based definition: Soil protection

Figure 8 Main agroecology agroecosystem-based definition soil protection type practices

Recommendation 6: Soil sustainable management

The sustainable soil production is essentially obtained through the adequate inputs of organic matter to overcome the intensive farming system soil decapitalization at medium and long term. Crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation and livestock diversification play an important role in obtaining these organic matter inputs without external amendments. The use of forest residues as a way to increase soil organic matter is also an excellent landscape nutrient cycling connection that improves sustainable soil fertility promotion that was traditionally used in Europe. Due to the huge soil degradation and the excess of mineral

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nutrient applied in European soils, the lack of chemicals use and the nutrient accountability is seen as essential.

Table 3 Agroecological diversification based systems explanation for soil physical protection

SOIL BIODIVERSITY								
Practice	Scale	land use	Type	Explanation	Main purpose	Description	Example	
SOIL PHYSICAL PROMOTION	No physical disturbance	agriculture	No tillage	direct sowing	avoid soil structure destruction, compaction	Manual and mechanical direct sowing leaving the previous crop residues	i.e. maize direct sowing	
		agriculture	Minimum tillage	soil labour affecting top soil	improve seeding success, avoid soil structure destruction	Reduced topsoil labour and manual and mechanical direct sowing	i.e. maize sowing	
	Crop use	woody crops/ herbaceous permanent crops	Permanent crops	use of deep root species	increase soil porosity, reduce compaction increase long term soil carbon	plant woody perennials (agroforestry) or deep rooted herbaceous plants	i.e. hedgerows	
Practice	Scale	land use	Type	Explanation	Main purpose	Description	Example	
SOIL CHEMICAL PROMOTION	Amendments	agriculture	Compost addition	high quality compost addition	Improve soil environment fertility	increase soil organic matter	i.e. urban or faarm residues compost	
	Organic fertilizers	agriculture	manure additon	N based organic fertilizers addition	Improve nutrient supply	increase nutrient availability and optimization use	i.e. dairy cow manure inputs	

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2.1.2.3.- Landscape agroecology-based biodiversity preservation

From an agroecosystem perspective, agroecology is a type of land management that can stand by itself on the use of the biodiversity, but due to the large historical degradation of the agricultural and forest systems in Europe, it is also essential to avoid some practices that destroy biodiversity and landscape level. The main preservation agroecological practices should be linked to:

2.1.2.3.1.- Minimization of conversion

The minimization of the conversion of land use from forest to agricultural lands but also from permanent crops or permanent grasslands towards arable crops, as these changes move from more biodiverse areas at aerial and underground level towards more simplified and less ecosystem services supply ecosystem.

2.1.2.3.2.- Nature preservation

Preserving nature specific habitats such as wetlands, peatlands, nature areas as they have a specific site conditions that is linked to specific and special biodiversity that should be protected.

2.1.2.3.3.- Soil protection

Avoiding bare soils, as this creates a homogeneous habitat poorly linked to biodiversity from an edaphic perspective that deals to soil quality reduction, nitrate leachate, etc..

2.2. Transformational agroecology phase: the food system level

The transformational agroecology phase is associated with the social part of agroecology, where knowledge exchange and work and investment sharing linked to social biodiversity and interaction is highly relevant. The social component agroecology promotion is deployed in three main pillars associated with

- (i) The horizontal knowledge sharing among the same and different types of stakeholders to reach an objective or multiple objectives.

The first pillar aims at reaching an objective or multiple objectives by sharing knowledge among peers but also among different types of stakeholders.

- (ii) Collaboration and cooperation among peers and among stakeholders types

Collaboration or cooperation among peers is key to reduce production costs associated to time and infrastructure savings, it also generates social networks. Collaboration among different types of stakeholders is key to promote

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(iii) Short and diversified value chains

Optimization of the use of resources within the food system should be as close to consumers as possible either reaching better relationships among value chain stakeholders or having a close product selling with regard to the consumers to promote short value chains

Recommendation 7. Food system management

Agroecology social definition is the dynamic social construction within and among actors that fosters knowledge and activities exchange processes and continuous learning among different stakeholders: producers, processors, retailers, advisors, researcher and consumers aiming at implementing the agroecology main principles or elements. The social movement associated with the agroecological elements should be fostered based on the horizontal knowledge sharing among peers and stakeholders, collaboration and cooperation among peers and stakeholders and the promotion of short and diversified value chains.

2.3. The CAP

2.3.1. CAP conditionality

2.3.1.1 CAP environment conditionality

The environment conditionality is divided in three main areas associated with the (i) Climate and environment, (ii) Public and plant health and (iii) the animal welfare. The new EU conditionality (2023-2027) is based on a set of standards for good agricultural environmental condition of land (GAEC) and statutory management requirement (SMR). Table 2 shows the classification of the GAEC and SMR attending the their main purpose within each Conditionality topic.

Table 4 Classification of GAEC (good agricultural environmental condition of land) and SMR (statutory management requirement) based on the CAP the purpose they have and the type of agroecological practice linked to the GAEC and the AE practice type positive effects on SMR.

Topic	Purpose	GAEC	GAEC description	AE biodiversity type
CLIMATE AND ENVIRONMENT	Biodiversity protection	GAEC 1	Permanent grassland maintenance	SB, CD
		GAEC 2	Protection of wetland and peatland	SB, CD
		GAEC 3	Ban on burning arable stubble	SB, CD
		GAEC 5	Tillage management	SB
		GAEC 9	Ban on converting or ploughing permanent grasslands in Natura 2000 sites	SB
		GAEC 6	Avoid bare soil	SB, CR
	Biodiversity enhancement	GAEC 6	Avoid bare soil	CR
		GAEC 4	Establishment of buffer strips along water courses	CD
		GAEC 7	Crop rotation	CR
		GAEC 8	Non-productive areas or features in agricultural areas	CD
	Purpose	SMR	SMR description	AE practice positive effect
	water protection	SMR 1	Control diffuse sources of pollution by phosphates	SB, CR, CD
		SMR 2	Water protection against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources	SP, CR, CD
Habitat protection	SMR 3	Wild birds conservation	CR, CD	
	SMR 4	Conservation of natural habitats and wild flora and fauna	CR, CD	
PUBLIC HEALTH AND PLANT HEALTH	Food safety	SMR 5	Food safety procedures	CR, CD
		SMR 6	Ban on the use of substances having a hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta antagonists	SB
	Plant protection	SMR 7	Plant protection products market	SB
		SMR 8	Sustainable use of pesticides and restrictions	SB, CR, CD
ANIMAL WELFARE	Animal protection	SMR 9	Minimum standards protecting calves	LD
		SMR 10	Minimum standards protecting pigs	LD
		SMR 11	Protection of animals kept for farming purposes	LD

2.3.1.1.1 GAEC

Agroecology has the potential to enhance climate change and environment. However, most of the GAEC aims at protecting the existing agroecosystem biodiversity to overcome and prevent the ecosystem damage caused either by intensification or land abandonment. For example, the maintenance of permanent grasslands is compulsory at state level to either increase carbon sequestration or avoid emissions, when transformed in arable lands, but at the same time protects and enhances crop diversification. GAEC standards target climate and environment the proposal of a set of goals that protect soils (SB), promote crop diversification (CD) and crop rotation to protect and enhance biodiversity.

2.3.1.1.1.1 Protecting biodiversity

Both **Permanent grassland maintenance** and the **Ban on converting or ploughing permanent grasslands in Natura 2002 sites** mean grazing and no ploughing therefore increasing biodiversity (trampling, urine and faeces distribution and animal selection (Buttler et al. 2009)) while also no tillage in soil and therefore enhancing soil protection. Both grazing and the lack of tillage increase soil carbon sequestration, that should be quantified to have a baseline to understand how the CAP money increased the permanent grassland maintenance

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at least in the marginal lands with autochthonous breeds (Rigueiro-Rodríguez et al. 2009). These benefits should also contribute to increase the extent of permanent grasslands and extensive farming systems. Moreover, permanent grassland is linked to grazing for adequate maintenance, therefore a measure that promotes livestock diversification (autochthonous breeds promotion) if marginal lands are grazed. The protection of peatlands and wetlands, banning burning arable stubble, tillage reduction, land ploughing and avoid bare soil are associated with the reduction of greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions while preserving existing soil biodiversity. The development of buffer strips, crop rotation and maintenance of landscape features in agricultural areas (including woody perennials associated with agroforestry practices) enhance biodiversity.

The **protection of wetlands and peatlands** are essential to further protect current systems against climate change, as both areas have large carbon stocks. Soil organic carbon stocks in the EU-27 are estimated that cover more than 593727 km² or the 5.5% of the land surface in Europe that stores over the 20% of the total terrestrial soil carbon stocks (Zak et al. 2022). Moreover, these habitats are associated to special and specific biodiversity that should be maintained.

Burn on burning arable stubble being a traditional practice in many areas it releases carbon directly to the atmosphere instead of being incorporated into the soil and depending on the temperature and timing of the burning will destroy soil fauna, flora and microbiological biodiversity. On the other side, there is the prescribed burning in shrublands that allows plants to rejuvenate the systems is the extension is not too large, this allows to increase biodiversity (as grasses combine with shrubs and to maintain the protected shrublands areas in good conditions to be preserved, this is known as pyric herbivory (Fuhlendorf 2008) as shown the EU projects Open2preserve, COMPAS and Pyric-Labs.

Tillage management, practices like minimum tillage and no tillage associated with permanent crops establishment or direct sowing reduces the soil carbon stock releases while maintaining the biodiversity as described by Kertesz and Madarasz (2014).

Avoid bare soil can be considered both a biodiversity protection tool that can be overcome by employing biodiversity in crop rotation agroecological practices. Bare soils are very poor habitats conducting to very poor biodiversity content that increases the risk of contamination (nitrate leaching) and soil erosion and therefore minimizing the ecosystem services delivery that should be avoided (Burkhard et al. 2019).

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2.3.1.1.1.2 Enhancing biodiversity

Besides **avoid bare soil** through the use of Crop rotation, **crop rotation** itself is also promoted as part of the GAEC 7. Moreover, crop diversification is enhanced by using agroforestry (**establishment of buffer strips along water courses** if woody) and the **development of non-productive areas or features in agricultural areas** that may be converted in productive areas if bioeconomy associated with those current non-productive areas is developed.

Recommendation 8: Standards for good agricultural and environmental condition of land (GAEC)

The current state of degradation of European ecosystems makes highly relevant all the GAEC proposals. However, the ones associated with permanent grasslands should be more ambitious and promote the expansion of the extent of this land whenever abandon land on marginal areas exist through extensive livestock farming systems in some Mediterranean areas. Adequate prescribed burning practices ensures shrublands health if carried out in small areas and combined with grazing. No-tillage, minimum tillage and avoiding bare soils are seen as a great measure to preserve the carbon but the introduction of woody perennials to enhance soil carbon stocks is needed in some degraded soils. More proactive GAEC initiatives such as buffer strips along water courses, crop rotation and the inclusion of non-productive areas or features in agricultural areas are more suitable for the current EU degraded soils and ecosystems.

2.3.1.1.2. SMR

SMRs are related to specific regulations of habitat and water protection that can be enhanced by crop rotation and crop diversification that may reduce the needs of external inputs increasing food safety and at the same time plant protection, therefore, contributing to the promotion of public and plant health. Animal protection is associated with the animal welfare linked to animals living in stables, but do not consider the fact that animal grazing is the best form to enhance animal welfare and protect permanent grasslands. The fact that fulfilment the brand of “animal welfare” SMR requisites is not associated with grazing systems cause a deleterious effect on these sustainable extensive farming systems.

2.3.1.1.2.1 Climate and environment

Those SMR associated with climate and habitat protection can be reached by implementing agroecology. For example, the **control of diffuse sources of pollution by phosphates (SMR1)** and the **water protection against pollution caused by nitrates from agricultural sources (SMR2)** should be controlled in origin when fertilization is carried out, but also, through the reduction of the need of fertilization by using the biodiversity. Therefore, the crop

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rotation, crop diversification and the soil biodiversity enhancement are seen as key elements to reach the aim of phosphorous but also nitrogen pollution, especially when deep rooted species such as woody perennials is used as agroforestry.

The SMR aiming at protecting habitats for special taxonomic groups such as **birds (SMR3)** but in general **flora and fauna (SMR4)** are highly relevant but easily linked mostly to soil biodiversity protection, crop diversification and crop rotation and considering the reduction of pollution they causes (see SMR 1 and 2) as mentioned before.

2.3.1.1.2.2 Public health and plant health

Food safety procedures (SMR5) as well the **ban of substances with hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta antagonists (SMR6)** are key to maintain human, animal and ecosystem health across the whole ecosystem nutrient and pollutants cycling that should be linked to the use of more sustainable agroecological practices. Agroecological practices such as crop rotation and crop diversification can broke the cycle of many parasites and microorganisms associated with the habitat modification, while woody perennial livestock grazing in particular can reduce the presence of some helminths parasites in the goats.

The lack of knowledge of biodiversity and the temporary and spatial ecological functions at plot and landscape the biodiversity makes necessary the use of **plant protection products and regulate the market (SMR7)** and determine the **sustainable use of pesticides and restrictions (SMR8)**. The simplification of the systems makes that pest have not natural enemies that diminishes the productivity of the crop. Multiproductive systems where different species are combined is the answer to reduce the impact of pests and weeds on productivity, while promoting diversified markets. The combination of cropland residues with grazing is also key to reduce pests impacts (example grazing uncommercial chestnut fruits after harvesting reduces chestnut diseases in the forthcoming years). Therefore to reduce the impact of plant protection products we should enhance the use of agroecology agroecosystem biodiversity based principles associated with crop rotation and crop diversification.

2.3.1.1.2.3 Animal welfare

The **SMR9, SMR10 and SMR11** are associated with the minimum standards of **calves, pigs and animals kept for faming purposes** are essential to maintain animal welfare and promote the organoleptic value of the animal products. However, these standards are provided to animals that are in stables. The indoor animals can claim the certificate of “animal welfare” that is not provided to animals that are grazing outdoors and protecting nature when benefiting from them. This causes a distortion in the markets not benefiting grazing as a key activity to

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enhance ecosystem services delivery in the fields. This is obtained by unofficial brands such as “milk pasture”, “woodlands eggs”.

Recommendation 9: Statutory management requirement (SMR)

The current state of degradation of European ecosystems, the needs of protecting health and ethically promote animal welfare makes highly relevant all the SMR proposals.

The links of the use of biodiversity to reduce the needs of fertilizers (water protection), and preserve habitats (for birds, flora and fauna) is not clearly shown. Therefore a lack of agroecological, biodiversity nature-based solutions are not linked to the SMR as the first step to reduce the SMR1 to 4 aims.

There is a lack of connection of the biodiversity potential and their respective ecological functions with the food safety and plant protection. SMR 1 to 8 should be clearly linked to crop rotation, crop diversification, soil preservation and adequate livestock grazing to reduce the degradation state of the European ecosystems from the very beginning in the CAP besides what is shown and enlarged in the eco-schemes or rural development methods.

The SMR 9 to 11 should promote grazing as a way to use and promote biodiversity at various levels and recognize the role extensive grazing systems with a *per se* brand of fulfilment of the animal welfare requisites that are linked to the plot, farm and landscape agroecological practices promotion.

2.3.1.2 CAP social conditionality

The CAP social conditionality is a new concept within the CAP that aims at enhancing the employment and promote the health and safety by promoting adequate working conditions including formation and health. Most of the rules are already compulsory in most of the EU member states but they are now compulsory to receive the direct payments and ensures the fulfilment through the written compromise of the farmers. They can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5 Employment and health and safety conditions of the 2023-2027 CAP

SOCIAL CONDITIONALITY	
EMPLOYMENT	Employment conditions
	Agricultural employment linked to an employment contract
	Employment contract provided within the first seven days of working
	Changes to the employment relationship to be provided in documentary form
	Probationary period
	Conditions regarding minimum predictability work
	Mandatory training
HEALTH AND SAFETY	General provision laying down duty of employer to ensure safety and health workers
	General obligation on employers to take measures necessary for safety and health protection, including prevention risks and provision of information and training
	Protective and preventive services: worker(s) to be designated for health and safety activities or competent external service to be engaged
	Employer to take measures for first aid, fire-fighting and evacuation of workers
	Obligations on employers regarding assessment of risks, protective measures and equipment , recording and reporting of occupational accidents
	Provision of information to workers on safety and health risks and protective and preventive measures
	Consultation and participation of workers in discussions on all questions relating to safety and health at work
	Employer to ensure that workers receive adequate safety and health training
	General obligations to ensure that work equipment is suitable for work to be carried out by workers without impairment of safety or health
	Rules concerning work equipment: must comply with the Directive and established minimum requirements and be adequately maintained
	Inspection of work equipment – equipment to be inspected after instalment and periodic inspections by competent persons
	Work equipment involving specific risks to be restricted to persons tasked with using it and all repairs, modifications, maintenance to be performed by designated workers
	Ergonomics and occupational health
	Workers to receive adequate information and, where appropriate, written instructions on use of work equipment
	Workers to receive adequate training

2.3.2. Pillar I CAP eco-schemes

The CAP ecoschemes establishes a set of voluntary interventions associated with the farmer direct payments that have a fund allocation of at least the 25% of the CAP. The ecoschemes should be designed in such a way that fulfils at least 2 out of the 7 areas shown in Table 6. The ecoschemes like happened with the GAEC and SMR are mostly linked to the objectives of climate change, habitat protection and health associated with the concept of enhanced conditionality. However, it does not include any social aspect. The way that the EU CAP regulation 2021/2115 is written allows member states to use agroecology as a way to reach the goals linked to climate change, habitats protection and health.

The European Union also provided members states with a inspiring list of potential agricultural practices that ecoschemes can support that are mostly linked to the agroecology implementation in agroecosystems: crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation and

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diversification and soil biodiversity preservation, enhancement and restoration. These practices should be linked to the objectives deployed in the different areas of environment, climate and animal welfare actions under the CAP strategic plans that can be seen in Table 6. The potential list of practices were initially associated to a set of “practices” that we organize in this document to facilitate the connection of land and livestock use practices (crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation, livestock diversification and soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration) with the potential contribution to the different target areas of the ecoschemes (climate change mitigation and adaptation, protection of improvement of water quality, prevention of soil degradation, protection of biodiversity, actions for a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides and actions to enhance animal welfare).

Table 6 Ecoscheme areas and link with the agroecological practice positive contribution. CR: Crop rotation; CD: Crop diversification, LR: Livestock rotation; LD: Livestock diversification; SP: Soil biodiversity protection, preservation and enhancement.

	ECOSCHEMES AREAS	AE biodiversity type
CLIMATE CHANGE	Climate change mitigation , including reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural practices, as well as maintenance of existing carbon stores and enhancement of carbon sequestration	CR, CD, SP
	Climate change adaptation , including actions to improve resilience of food production systems and animal and plant diversity for stronger resistance to diseases and climate change	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD
HABITATS PROTECTION	Protection or improvement of water quality and reduction of pressure on water resources	CR, CD, SP
	Prevention of soil degradation, soil restoration, improvement of soil fertility and of nutrient management and soil biota	CR, CD, SP, LR
	Protection of biodiversity, conservation or restoration of habitats or species , including maintenance and creation of landscape features or non-productive areas	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD
	Actions for a sustainable and reduced use of pesticides , in particular pesticides that present a risk for human health or environment	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD
HEALTH	Actions to enhance animal welfare or combat antimicrobial resistance	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD

2.3.2.1 Crop rotation ecoscheme based practices

The crop rotation practice associated with the ecoscheme topic and name list provided by the European commission (2021) and their link to the main ecoscheme areas can be seen in Table 7

Table 7 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to crop rotation and associated with the areas of a:mitigation, b:adaptation, c:water protection, d: Soil protection and improvement, e:biodiversity protection and restoration, f: sustainable and reduced use of pesticides,

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g: actions to enhance animal welfare. Light and dark green shade shows the EU and AE4EU areas that the specific practice fulfills, respectively. The dark green have an explanation for the inclusion

Ecoschem topic	Ecoscheme name		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	Reason behind including extra benefits
IPM	Land lying fallow with species composition for biodiversity purpose	CR								if woody species appears (a), biodiverse areas prevent from soil degradation
Agroecology	Crop rotation with leguminous crops	CR								rotation reduces water leaching (c), i.e. cover crops
Agroecology	Winter soil cover and catch crops above conditionality	CR								Biodiverse systems increased optimal use of the resources (a) increasing soil organic matter inputs (d)

The ecoscheme practices associated with the crop rotation have the aim of increasing biodiversity (laying fallow), soil fertility (legume use) and reduce nitrate leaching (winter and catch crops) that can be combined with crop biodiversity. The CR practices are able to fulfil all ecoscheme areas with the exception of animal welfare as it is related to crop rotation.

Figure 9 shows the number of ecoschemes interventions promoting crop rotation. In the first year of the CAP 2023-2027 strategic plans, Spain (6), followed by Slovenia (2) Finland (82) and France, Lithuania and Belgium (1) the unique ones that promoted crop rotation.

Figure 9 Number of ecoscheme interventions promoting crop rotation in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.2.2 Crop diversification ecoscheme based practices

Table 8 shows the list of ecoschemes associated with crop diversification. The types of crop diversification promoted by the EU are linked to the use of different varieties, vegetation strips with different aims (pollination, erosion), with pasture promotion related to permanent grasslands.

Table 8 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to crop diversification and associated with the areas of a: mitigation, b: adaptation, c: water protection, d: Soil protection and improvement, e: biodiversity protection and restoration, f: sustainable and reduced use

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of pesticides, g: actions to enhance animal welfare.. Light and dark green shade shows the EU and AE4EU areas that the specific practice fulfills, respectively. The dark green have an explanation for the inclusion

Ecoscheme topic	Ecoschem name		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	reason
IPM	Buffer strips with management practices and without pesticide	CD								buffer strips prevent soil degradation (d)
IPM	Increased use of resilient, pest resistant crop varieties and species	CD								reducing use of inputs (a, e), resistant species reduces the use of pesticides(f)
Agroecology	Mixed cropping -multi cropping	CD								If wood species appears but also multiple species sequester more carbon than monocrops because uses different resources(a), avoiding nutrient leaching (g)
Agroecology	Cover crop between tree rows on permanent crops- orchards, vineyards, olive trees - above conditionality	CD								If grazed enhances animal welfare (g)
Agroecology	Use of crops/plant varieties more resilient to climate change	CD								If more resilient, better use resources, mitigates climate change(a), being adapted prevent soil degradation (d)
Agroecology	Mixed species/diverse sward of permanent grassland for biodiversity purpose (pollination, birds, game feedstocks)	CD								
Agroforestry	Establishment and maintenance of high biodiversity silvopastoral systems	CD								Vegetal landscape features presence (trees, shrubs, etc...) increases carbon sequestration mitigating climate change (a), adequate shade increases the length of the growing season (b), increases the uptake of the excess of nutrient protecting waters (g), increases soil organic matter inputs (d) as it increases soil organic matter inputs protects soils and enhance soil health reduces the appearance of weeds (f)
Carbon farming	Extensive use of permanent grassland	CD								Grazing with adequate stocking rates enhance animal health It is related to climate change mitigation (a), water protection diminishing the manure production (g), protecting from soil degradation if adequate stocking rates are promoted (d), and provides animal welfare (g)
Carbon farming	Establishment and maintenance of permanent grassland	CD								Grazing with adequate stocking rates enhance animal health It is related to climate change adaptation (b), and provides animal welfare (g).
Protecting water resources	Managing crop water demand (switching to less water intensive crops, changing planting dates, optimises irrigation schedules)	CD								
Other practices beneficial for soil	Erosion prevention strips and wind breaks	CD								If vegetal strips are planned (trees, shrubs, etc...), the practice will increase carbon sequestration mitigating climate change (a), improves warr use due to the reduction of the dissection effect of winds (c), reduces the appearance of annual weeds due to shading (f) and provides animal welfare (g)
Other practices beneficial for soil	Establishment or maintenance of terraces and strip cropping	CD								If vegetal strips are planned (trees, shrubs, etc...), the practice will increase carbon sequestration mitigating climate change (a), improves warr use due to the reduction of the dissection effect of winds (c), reduces the appearance of annual weeds due to shading (f) and provides animal welfare (g)

The number of ecoscheme interventions promoting crop diversification is much more relevant than those enhancing crop rotation. The number of interventions associate with crop diversification are specially large in large countries such as Spain, Germany or France, but low in Ireland, The Netherlands, or some eastern countries (Czech Republic, Slovakia and Hungary).

Figure 10 Number of ecoscheme interventions promoting crop diversification in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.2.3 Soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration based ecoschemes

Table 9 presents the list of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission linked to soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration. Most of the soil protection and

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production ecoschemes are associated with the optimal use of the resources. Only one of the ecoscheme practices related to soil is linked to the physical preservation as part of the conservation agriculture.

Table 9 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to crop diversification and associated with the areas of a:mitigation, b:adaptation, c:water protection, d: Soil protection and improvement, e:biodiversity protection and restoration, f: sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, g: actions to enhance animal welfare. Light and dark green shade shows the EU and AE4EU areas that the specific practice fulfills, respectively. The dark green have an explanation for the inclusion

Ecoscheme topic	Ecoschem name		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	reason
Carbon farming	Conservation agriculture	SP								Conservation agriculture protects soils and increases soil organic matter improving the temperature and humidity stability in the soils (b)
Carbon farming	Appropriate management of residues i.e. burying of agricultural residues, seeding on residues	SP								Burying agricultural residues increases the soil organic matter improving the temperature and humidity stability in the soils (b) and enhancing soil biodiversit (e).
Precision farming	Nutrients management plan, use of innovative approaches to minimise nutrient release, optimal pH for nutrient uptake, circular agriculture	SP								Adequate nutrient management protects soil biodiversity (e).
Precision farming	Precision crop farming to reduce inputs (fertilisers, water, plant protection products)	SP								Reducing nutrient inputs is related to climate change mitigation due to the non-renewable resource uses to develop (N) and transport (P) fertilizers (a), protects water from nutrient leaching avoidance (c), protects from soil degradation and reduces external inputs (fertiliser, pesticides) (d), and promotes animal welfare as less chemical inputs are available in the environment if the grass or crops are grazed (g)
Improve nutrient management	Implementation of nitrates-related measures that go beyond the conditionality obligations	SP								Reducing nutrient inputs is related to climate change mitigation due to the non-renewable resource uses to develop (N) and transport (P) fertilizers (a)
Improve nutrient management	Measures to reduce and prevent water, air and soil pollution from excess nutrients such as soil sampling if not already obligatory, creation of nutrient traps	SP								

Figure 11 shows the number of ecoscheme interventions promoting soil biodiversity associated with the increase of the organic matter, the reduction of the use of pesticides and the lack of promotion of soil tillage. From all soil ecoscheme intervaneitons, the increase of soil organic matter and the reduction of pesticides are more selected by the member states than the soil tillage use.

Figure 11 Number of ecoscheme interventions promoting soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration in the CAP 2023-2027

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2.3.2.4 Livestock and grazing ecoscheme based practices

Table 10 shows the list of ecoschemes linked to livestock and grazing ecoschemes. Out of the 6 practices linked to livestock, the two first are associated with the animal health preservation that can be obtained through grazing. The last four are related to grazing promotion.

Table 10 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to livestock rotation and diversification and associated with the areas of a:mitigation, b:adaptation, c:water protection, d: Soil protection and improvement, e:biodiversity protection and restoration, f: sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, g: actions to enhance animal welfare. Light and dark green shade shows the EU and AE4EU areas that the specific practice fulfills, respectively. The dark green have an explanation for the inclusion.

Ecoscheme topic	Ecoschem name		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	reason
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Practices increasing animal robustness, fertility, longevity and adaptability, e.g. lifespan of dairy cows; breeding lower emission animals, promoting genetic diversity and resilience	LD								Breeding animals with lower emissions causes a better water (c), soil (d) protection, soil biodiversity (e), and increase soil biodiversity (f)
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Animal health prevention and control plans: overall plan for reducing the risk of infections that require antimicrobials and coverign all relevant husbandry practices, e.g. crawl space between two raring belts, vaccination and treatments, enhanced bioscurity, use of feed additives, etc.	LR								As grazing is part of the techniques to enhance animal health it is related to climate change mitigation (a), adaptation (b), water protection diminishing the manure production (c), protecting from soil degradation if adequate stocking rates are promoted (d), increasing soil biodiversity (e) and reducing the needs of pesticides (f)
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Providing access to pastures and increasing grazing period for grazing animals	LR								Grazing with adequate stoking rates enhance animal health it is related to water protection diminishing the manure production (c), protecting from soil degradation if adequate stocking rates are promoted (d), increasing soil biodiversity (e) and reducing the needs of pesticides (f)
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Provide and manage regular access to open air areas	LR								Grazing with adequate stoking rates enhance animal health it is related to climate change mitigation (a), adaptation (b), water protection diminishing the manure production (c), protecting from soil degradation if adequate stocking rates are promoted (d), increasing soil biodiversity (e) and reducing the needs of pesticides (f)
High nature value (HNV) farming	Shepherding on open spaces and between permanent crops, transhumance and commong grazing	LR								Grazing with adequate stocking rates enhance animal health and permanent pastures that enhances climate change mitigation (a)
Agroecology	Low intensity grass-based livestock system	LR								Grassland biodivesty is enhanced with adequate stocking rate generating animal health (e).

The number of interventions enhancing livestock diversification and rotation is much lower than those associated with crop rotation and diversification (Figure 12). They are specially important in Rumania. Large countries such as Spain, France or Germany do not promote livestock agroecological practices by the agroecological interventions. Specially relevant in Portugal, Italy, Greece in the Mediterranean areas, in Belgium in the Atlantic zone and in various Eastern European countries.

Figure 12 Number of ecoscheme interventions promoting livestock rotation or diversification in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.2.5 Overall Crop Rotation, Crop Diversification, Soil protection and Livestock and grazing ecoscheme based practices

Table 11 shows the practices associated with the mix of different types of ecoscheme list. The first four practices are linked to organic farming that can and may use all the agroecological practices as a way to ensure biodiversity. The last four are linked to the use of biodiversity in between croplands that may use all crop rotation and crop diversification that enhances soil health and may be used by livestock and grasslands. Besides those, there is the possibility of low intensity management of crops to reduce fertilizer that may be combined with the use of crop rotation, crop diversification enhancing soil health and animal welfare.

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Table 11 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to crop and livestock rotation and diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration and associated with the areas of a: mitigation, b: adaptation, c: water protection, d: Soil protection and improvement, e: biodiversity protection, f: sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, g: actions to enhance animal welfare. Light green shade shows the EU areas that the specific practice fulfills.

Ecoscheme topic	Ecoscheme name		a	b	c	d	e	f	g	reason
Farm level	Conversion to organic farming	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								reducing use of inputs (a, e)
Farm level	Maintenance of organic farming	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								avoiding the use of inputs (a,e)
Agroecology	Practices and standards as set under organic farming rules	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								reducing use of inputs (a, e), if livestock involved (g)
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Practices and standards as set under organic farming rules	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								avoiding the use of inputs (a,e)
High nature value (HNV) farming	Reduction of fertiliser use, low intensity management in arable crops	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								
Agroforestry	Establishment and maintenance of landscape features above conditionality	CR, CD, SP, LR, LD								Adequate shade reduces the peak heat damage to cereals (i.e. wheat) grain production (b), the appearance of annual weeds (f) and provides animal welfare (g)
Agroforestry	Management and cutting plan of landscape features	CD, SP, LR								Vegetal landscape features presence (trees, shrubs, etc) increases carbon sequestration mitigating climate change (a), adequate shade reduces the peak heat damage to cereals (i.e. wheat) grain production (b), increases the uptake of the excess of nutrient protecting waters (c), increases soil organic matter inputs (d) and provides animal welfare (g)
High nature value (HNV) farming	Land lying fallow with species composition for biodiversity purpose (pollination, birds, game feestocks, etc)	CR, CD								Biodiverse systems increases the optimal use of the resources (a) increasing the soil organic matter inputs)
High nature value (HNV) farming	Semi-natural habitat creation and enhancement	CD, LR								

2.3.2.6 No agroecology related ecoscheme based practices

Table 12 shows the list of ecoschemes detailed in the European Commission (2021) list as practices that are directly related to agroecology. Most of them are associated with the housing conditions of livestock, the water management and mechanical weed control no based in ecological practices.

Table 12 List of ecoschemes provided by the European Commission (2021) linked to crop and livestock rotation and diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration and associated with the areas of a: mitigation, b: adaptation, c: water protection, d: S: Soil protection and improvement, e: biodiversity protection, f: sustainable and reduced use of pesticides, g: actions to enhance animal welfare. Light green shade shows the EU areas that the specific practice fulfills.

Ecoschem topic	Ecoscheme name	a	b	c	d	e	f	g
IPM	Mechanical weed control							
Agroecology	Improved rice cultivation to decrease methane emissions (e.b. alternate wet and dry techniques)							
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Feeding plans: suitability of and access to feed and water, feed and water quality analyses (e.g. micotoxiens), optimised feed strategies							
Husbandry and animal welfare plans	Friendly housing conditions: increased space allowances per animal, improved flooring (e.g. straw bedding provided on a daily basis), free farrowing, provision of enriched environment (e.g. rooting for pigs, perching, nest-building materials, etc.), shaing/sprinklers/ventilation to cope with heat stress							
Carbon farming	Rewetting weatlands/peatlands, paludiculture							
Carbon farming	Minimum water table level during winter							
Precision farming	Improving irrigation efficiency							
Other practices related to GHG emissions	Feed additives to decrease emissions from enteric fermentation							
Other practices related to GHG emissions	Improves manure management and storage							

Recommendation 10: Ecoschemes

The ecoschemes list proposed by the European Commission are mostly linked to the agroecological practices associated with crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation, livestock diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration. From those livestock diversification is not presented as part of the ecoschemes. Moreover, there are several practices that may involve all agroecological biodiversity-based practices, but they

are not detailed enough. The involvement of forest lands as suppliers of fertility to agronomic land, the use of livestock as a way to increase the nutrient cycling and above all of them to improve soil health should be better detailed.

2.3.3. Pillar II

2.3.3.1 *Agroecosystems rural development interventions*

Table 13 shows the main activities associated with the agroecosystem level of agroecology to be expanded from what was fulfilled in the Conditionality and in the eco-scheme proposals. The Rural Development program can be associated with climate change and habitat protection. Habitat protection have two main types of interventions the natural or other area-specific constraints or those areas with specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements.

Table 13 Types of agroecosystem based interventions of the Rural Development Programme associated with the CAP 2023-2027

	Types of intervention for rural development
CLIMATE CHANGE	Environmental, climate related and other management commitments
HABITATS PROTECTION	Natural or other area-specific constraints
	Areas-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements

2.3.3.1.1. Climate change interventions

The climate change interventions associated with the Rural Development programme of the CAP 2023-2027 were also structured following the main agroecosystem based agroecology practices established in the section 2.1 of this report: crop rotation and diversification, soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration and livestock rotation and diversification.

2.3.3.1.1.1. Crop rotation interventions

Crop rotation promotion by the rural development interventions of the CAP 2023-2027 can be seen in the Figure 13. Crop rotation is promoted by the 9% of the interventions and are linked mostly to France and implemented in a large number of regions in Europe. Compared with the previous CAP (2014-2020), the CAP 2023-2027 promotes much more the crop rotation agroecological practices. The reasons behind the use of crop rotation in the previous CAP were to improve water quality, improving soil fertility and health and sustainability. These reasons within the CAP 2023-2027 were the maintenance of the natural habitats soil protection (including soil erosion and restoration), water protection, organicic farming promotion, the biodiversity preservation including habitats and pollinators and an alternative use to pesticides.

Figure 13 Number of rural development interventions promoting crop rotation in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.1.2. Crop diversification interventions

The Crop diversification interventions promoted by the CAP 2023-2027 can be seen in the Figure 14. The percentage of the total measures implementing crop diversification was very high (47%), being the agroecology practice intervention more used across Europe. As happened with the crop rotation, the crop diversification interventions were more spread in the CAP 2023-2027 than in the CAP 2014-2020. The main reasons for using crop diversification were the maintenance of natural habitats, nature conservation, the integrated

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production, the management of grassland in an extensive form, the use of agroforestry and forestry but also the use of diversification in crops and the protection of crop diversity through the protection of germoplasm banks.

Figure 14 Number of rural development interventions promoting crop diversification in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.1.3. Livestock diversification

Livestock diversification promotion by the different CAP 2023-2027 interventions can be seen in the Figure 15. The rural development widely promotes livestock diversification mainly associated with the preservation of autochthonous breeds across Europe. Livestock diversification is largely implemented in Europe, representing the 17% of the interventions of the whole Europe. The unique large country with a low implementation of this livestock diversification agroecology related interventions was Germany, Czech Republic, Slovakia and Bulgaria.

Only France promotes the integration of livestock with the arable and grassland fields connecting this two types of territories and therefore promoting the nutrient cycling and the circular economy.

Figure 15 Number of rural development interventions promoting livestock diversification in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.1.4. Soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration

Figure 16 shows the main types of rural development interventions associated with soil protection. The reduction of the use of pesticides as well as fertilizers are more spreadly promoted that the addition of organic amendments, which is the basis for sustainable agriculture, while soil physical rotation is less promoted.

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Figure 16 Number of rural development interventions promoting soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration rotation in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.2. Habitat protection interventions

2.3.3.1.1.1. Natural or other area-specific constraints

Figure 17 shows the amount of areas with interventions allocation to natural areas or areas with specific constraints. Most of the countries implement this type of intervention but there are some like Ireland, Germany, The Netherlands, Czech Republic, Hungary, Estonia, Latvia and Sweden that do not implement it.

Figure 17 Number of rural development interventions promotion of natural or other area-specific constraints in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.1.2. Areas-specific disadvantages resulting from certain mandatory requirements

Figure 18 shows the number of areas promoting compensatory payments for Natura 2000, that are mostly implemented in central and the South of Europe.

Figure 18 Number of rural development interventions promoting areas-specific disadvantages in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.1.3. Other agroecosystem interventions

Figure 19 shows some agroecological practices that are promoted through global measures like for esample the improvement of the efficiency of water management enhancing water quality and availability that improves the agricultural lands ecosystem services provision. Wate management is usually linked to the south and north of Europe. Other interventions like the promotion of organic farming can be linked to any of the agroecology practices. Finally animal welfare is usually associated with the promotion of animal welfare in stables and not linked to graing.as a practice in Europe.

Figure 19 Number of rural development interventions promoting water management, organic farming and animal welfare in the CAP 2023-2027

Recommendation 11: Agroecosystem based Rural Development interventions

The current open rural development interventions associated with the CAP 2023-2027 are mostly linked to the agroecological practices associated with crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock diversification and soil protection, enhancement and restoration. From those livestock rotation is not presented as part of the rural development interventions. There is a lack of promotion of the connectivity among different types of lands by using livestock or forest residues that are incipiently promoted in France and that are needed to fulfil the agroecological principles.

2.3.3.2 Social rural development interventions.

Besides the agroecosystem level, the agroecology is associated with a strong social component, that have three pillars:

- 1.- Horizontal knowledge sharing among different types of stakeholders to reach and objective
- 2.- Collaboration and cooperation among peers and with the same type of stakeholders to optimize the use of the resources.
- 3.- Use of short and diversified value chains.

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The social rural development deals with some of the social CAP objectives associated with the Rural Areas development by ensuring farmer renewal and the development of rural business models, the food and health sovereignty through the risk management tools and cooperation. Moreover, the social rural development has a specific intervention linked to the knowledge exchange and dissemination information (Figure 1). The social rural development programme has around 253 interventions.

However, the types of interventions of rural development are not directly linked to the reconnection of consumers and producers through the development of alternative food networks and even less with the building of new global food system based on participation, localness, fairness and justice.

Table 14 Structure of the social Rural Development interventions

RURAL DEVELOPMENT INTERVENTIONS	
INVESTMENTS	Investments, including investments in irrigation
RURAL EMPLOYMENT	Setting-up young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-up
TOOLS	Risk management tools
KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE	Cooperation
	Knowledge exchange and dissemination of the information

The social rural development interventions linked to the setting-up of young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-ups can be linked to agroecological practices such as short value chains, the cooperation can be associated with the collaboration among peers and the knowledge exchange and dissemination of the information can related to the horizontal knowledge sharing among different types of stakeholders to reach and objective.

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The Figure 20 shows the number of rural development interventions associated with the social agroecology perspective that are higher for the establishment of risk management tools, farmers interactions, cooperation and knowledge sharing.

Figure 20 Rural Development social number of interventions excepting investments

The global analysis of the type of social rural development interventions can be seen in the Figure 21. From this, it can be seen that the rural development interventions are associated with land management, environment, investments, value chains sectors and livestock in this order.

Figure 21 Rural Development social number of interventions associated with different topics

2.3.3.2.1. Investments including investments in irrigation

Figure 22 shows the number of interventions linked to investments that are associated with agricultural or not agricultural in rural areas. The number of interventions are restricted to

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few countries, being both types of investments (agricultural and no agricultural areas) only promoted in Germany.

Figure 22 Rural Development number of interventions associated with investments

Figure 23 shows the proportion of investments associated with agriculture or not, meaning that the 12% of the total interventions are linked to the improvement of the quality of life.

Figure 22 Agriculture and no agriculture rural investments share

The investments associated with the watersheds are mainly placed in the Mediterranean area, while those associated with environment are linked to a set of high biodiverse countries (Figure 24).

Figure 23 Rural Development number of interventions associated with watershed and environmental investments

Figure 25 details the share of environment investments. Water efficiency improvement represents the 7% of the total set of social interventions.

Figure 24 Environment investments promoted by the rural development interventions of the CAP 2023-2027

Figure 26 shows the most relevant types of investments associated with the rural investments (Forest), product investments (quality) and rural-urban areas promotion through the development of smart villages. With the exception of forest investments, all the relevant non agricultural investments are restricted to a very few number of countries.

Figure 25 Types of investments interventions

Figure 27 presents the share of forest and agroforestry as part of the promotion of the interventions for land management. It can be seen that forestry investments are larger than agroforestry.

Figure 26 Forest and agroforestry land management investment share

2.3.3.2.2 Young farmers and new farmers and rural business start-up

The development of a social measure linked to young farmers, also as part of the direct payments is key for the replacement of farms in an elderly European Union. Business start-ups are mostly associated with the development of new products, and bioeconomy which are highly relevant, but they are not interventions linked to short value chains or participatory

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approaches linked to the food system. Aspects like product diversification that ensures food security are not directly promoted.

The Figure 28 shows the share of the interventions associated with the promotion of the value chains, food quality, bioeconomy and circular economy with all of them having a similar share excepting the circular economy.

Figure 27 Value chain interventions typology share.

Figure 29 shows the interventions associated with the rural development programme that directly supports short value chains, which is restricted to very few eastern countries.

Figure 28 Rural development interventions supporting short value chains in the CAP 2023-2027

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2.3.3.2.3 Risk Management tools

Figure 30 shows the map of the rural development interventions promoting risk management tools. This is the most popular intervention of the social ones that is well developed in Italy, but also in France and Portugal or Germany and Poland. However, it is not implemented in large countries like Spain.

Figure 29 Rural development interventions supporting risk management tools in the CAP 2023-2027

2.2.3.3 Cooperation

The cooperation projects and collective investments are implemented in large countries like Spain, France, Germany, Sweden and Finland but not implemented in most of Europe (Figure 30).

Figure 30 Rural development interventions supporting cooperation projects and collective investments in the CAP 2023-2027

2.3.3.2.4. Knowledge exchange and dissemination of information

The producer organizations and networking interventions can be seen in the Figure 32. This type of information is relatively important in the Mediterranean countries but also in the northern countries such as Poland, Finland, Estonia, Lithuania and Latvia.

Figure 31 Rural development interventions supporting producer organizations and networking by the CAP 2023-2027

The promotion of operational groups by the intervention of the CAP 2023-2027 can be seen in the Figure 33, that shows a low number of countries implementing the operational groups. This is probably due to the fact that there is still some operational groups implementation in the previous CAP 2014-2020.

Figure 32 Rural development interventions supporting operational groups by the CAP 2023-2027

Recommendation 12: Food system based Rural Development interventions

The current open social rural development interventions associated with the CAP 2023-2027 are somehow promoting social agroecological aspects linked to the knowledge transfer and fostering interactions among different types of stakeholders and promoting short value chains. However, this is limited to a short number of countries.

The agroecological analysis of the initial activities and open interventions developed within the CAP 2023-2027 allow us to conclude:

- 1.- Agroecology can be identified with elements associated with the agroecosystem and the social part of the Rural Development areas
- 2.- With regard to the agroecosystem agroecological practices identification they can be linked to: crop rotation, crop diversification, livestock rotation, livestock diversification, soil biodiversity protection, enhancement and restoration. All of them are generally associated with the conditionality, ecoschemes and the agroecosystem based rural development interventions.
- 3.- The most important concerns with regard to the agroecosystem agroecological practices is the fact that they are not promoted in all countries, but also the lack of promotion of the connectivity among different types of lands by using livestock.
- 4.- With regard to the social agroecological practices they can be identified in three main pillars (a).- Horizontal knowledge sharing among different types of stakeholders to reach and objective, (b) Collaboration and cooperation among peers and with the same type of

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stakeholders to optimize the use of the resources and (c) Use of short and diversified value chains. They can only be briefly identified in the social rural development interventions.

5.- Compared with the agroecosystem agroecological practices, the social agroecological practices are much less developed and value chain diversification poorly promoted.

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